

Prioritizing Green Business Startup Ideas for University Students through the Integrated Multi-Criteria Model GANTT - EFAS - FUZZY - AHP – TOPSIS

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Abstract

In the trend of globalization associated with the need for innovation and sustainable development, starting a green business has become a strategic direction for university students - young people who have the ability to approach innovative thinking and are sensitive to environmental and social issues. However, choosing a green startup idea is not simply a process of developing creative ideas, but also requires a multi-criteria evaluation system to balance environmental, economic, feasibility and practicality factors. On that basis, this study builds and applies an integrated decision-making model including GANTT (evaluating ideal progress), EFAS (analyzing external environmental factors), FUZZY - AHP (standardizing weights of criteria under uncertain conditions), and TOPSIS (ranking optimal choices). The model is deployed to survey 1,000 students from 50 universities in Hanoi, thereby providing a scientific basis for ranking and selecting green business startup ideas suitable for students' conditions and capabilities.

Keywords: *Starting a business, choosing green business startup ideas, GANNT model, EFAS matrix, FUZZY - AHP model, TOPSIS model, FUZZY - AHP - TOPSIS model.*

JEL Classification codes: *O13, O33, Q01.*

Suggested citation: Dung, T.T., Nhi, N.N.B., Uyen, H.T., Van, P.A., Hang, V.T., & Nam, N.H. (2025). Prioritizing Green Business Startup Ideas for University Students through the Integrated Multi-Criteria Model GANTT - EFAS - FUZZY - AHP – TOPSIS. *European Journal of Management, Economics and Business*, 2(4), 142-149. DOI: 10.59324/ejm eb.2025.2(4).11

Introduction

Sustainable development poses new requirements for business start-ups, which are becoming a trend suitable for students - a young force rich in creativity and social responsibility. However, choosing a green business start-up idea requires evaluating many complex criteria such as feasibility, attractiveness and sustainability, etc. In this reality, this study proposes an integrated model of GANTT - EFAS - FUZZY - AHP - TOPSIS to support the process of making decisions to select ideas in a systematic, objective and effective manner.

Theoretical Basis of GANTT – EFAS – FUZZY – AHP – TOPSIS Models

The GANTT model is a project management tool developed by Henry L. Gantt in the early 20th century, used to determine the ideal business start-up timeline.

EFAS is used as a tool to evaluate external environmental factors affecting business start-up ideas.

FUZZY logic theory was first proposed by Zadeh, L.A. in 1965. This theory solves problems very close to the way people think. To date, FUZZY logic theory is used to standardize subjective qualitative assessments from experts or students.

AHP is a multi-criteria decision-making method developed by Professor Thomas L. Saaty in the 1970s. It is used to evaluate and choose between alternative business ideas based on various criteria.

TOPSIS is another multi-criteria decision-making method developed to rank alternatives based on their similarity to the ideal solution. In this study, it is used to rank the priority of green business ideas.

Research Methods

The study was conducted from April 24, 2025 to May 15, 2025 to survey 1,000 students at 50 Universities and Colleges in Hanoi, including 39 public schools and 11 private schools. The survey results showed that 538 people started businesses in the commercial sector, 240 people started businesses in the service sector, 185 people started businesses in the manufacturing sector, and 37 people started businesses in the agriculture, forestry and fishery sector.

Table 1. List of 50 Universities Participating in the Survey

University name	Type of university	University name	Type of university
Vietnam National University Ha Noi	Public school	Trade Union University	Private school
Hanoi University of Science and Technology	Public school	Hanoi Metropolitan University	Private school
University of Science and Technology of Hanoi	Public school	Hanoi Open University	Private school
Hanoi National University of Education	Public school	VietNam University of Traditional Medicine	Private school
Thuongmai University	Public school	Hanoi University of Public Health	Private school
University of Pharmacy	Public school	National Academy of Education Management	Private school
Banking Academy of Vietnam	Public school	Hanoi University of Natural Resources and Environment	Private school
National Economics University	Public school	Academy Of Policy and Development	Private school
Thuyloi University	Public school	Vietnam National University of Forestry	Private school
Hanoi University of Mining and Geology	Public school	Diplomatic Academy of Vietnam	Private school
Foreign Trade University	Public school	Hanoi University of Culture	Private school
Academy of Finance	Public school	University of Industrial Fine Art	Private school
Posts and Telecommunications Institute of Technology	Public school	Hanoi Industrial Textile Garment University	Private school
Vietnam National University of Agriculture	Public school	Vietnam National Academy of Music	Private school
Electric Power University	Public school	Thang Long University	Private school
Hanoi University of Industry	Public school	Phenikaa University	Private school

Hanoi University of Civil Engineering	Public school	Financing and Promoting Technology Education	Private school
Academy of Journalism and Communication	Public school	Phuong Dong University	Private school
Hanoi Medical University	Public school	Dai Nam University	Private school
VNU University of Law	Public school	Hanoi Financial And Banking University	Private school
University of Transport and Communications	Public school	Nguyen Trai University	Private school
University of Transport Technology	Public school	East Asia University of Technology	Private school
University of Labour Social Affairs	Public school	Hanoi University of Business and Technology	Private school
Hanoi Architectural University	Public school	Thanh Do University	Private school
Vietnam Women's Academy	Public school	Dong Do University	Private school

Source: Proposal of the author group

Research Results

The survey results show that: In terms of business start-up: commerce is the dominant field (53.8%). This is the field that attracts the most students in business start-up activities. The reason may be because the initial investment capital requirement is lower than that of manufacturing. The service sector (24%) has the potential to expand, including: study consulting, tutoring, phone and computer repair, beauty, small transportation... This is an area suitable for students with professional skills or talents. The manufacturing sector (18.5%) is difficult to start a business but has high value. Students who choose manufacturing often have a design-manufacturing, product processing mindset or have creative ideas for making handmade products. The agriculture-forestry-fishery sector (3.7%) may be a potential sector but few people choose it. This sector accounts for a low percentage mainly because: Implementation conditions require land and natural resources; Students mainly study in urban areas so there are few opportunities for practice.

Regarding business startup ideas, the most popular ideas were opening a bakery (10.9%) and selling clothes online (8.0%). The least popular ideas were opening a supermarket and opening a 3D printing shop (0.5%). Business areas mainly focused on trade, services and retail. This shows that students have chosen a wide variety of business ideas, ranging from traditional fields such as food, clothing, cosmetics, tutoring to modern and specialized fields such as 3D printing, medical therapy, and essential oil processing. Popular business ideas among students are small models, easy to do, low cost, and fast capital turnover.

Table 2. Table of Selected Business Sectors in the Start-Up sector Group

Business field	Business industry	Selected survey business sectors for evaluation	
<i>Manufacture</i>	Food production	-Open a bakery -Process aromatic oils	-Sell yogurt and nut milk
<i>Commerce</i>	Traditional trade	- Sell handmade goods - Open a shoe store - Sell sports goods - Sell electronic equipment - Open a grocery store - Sell jewelry accessories - Sell ornamental plants - Sell ornamental fish - Textile store	- Open a furniture store - Open a construction materials store - Open a phone store - Open a souvenir/office product store - Sell electronic components - Sell furniture - Sell swimwear

		- Open a diaper and milk store	- Sell medicinal herbs
	Electronic commerce	- Sell clothes online - Sell cosmetics online	- Sell books online - Sell online
<i>Service</i>	Educational services	- Open cooking class	- Tutor
	Health care services	- Open a hair salon	- Open spa, nail salon
	Marketing services	- Event organization company	
	Catering services	- Open a drink shop - Open a snack shop - Restaurant business	- Selling snacks - Opening a rice shop - Selling kimbap
	Design service	- Fashion design	- Painting service on request
	Entertainment services	- Photographer	
<i>Agriculture - forestry - fishery</i>	Crop	- Growing spices and medicinal plants	

Source: Compiled by the author group

Regarding the ideal average time for the stages in starting a business, based on the GANNT chart, we have: Exploring and forming ideas takes an ideal average time of 1.9 months; Market research takes an ideal average time of 2.1 months; Business planning takes an ideal average time of 2.097 months; Carrying out legal procedures and licenses takes an ideal average time of 2.04 months; Marketing and brand development takes an ideal average time of 2.23 months.

The results of the EFAS matrix analysis show that, in the process of starting a business, it is necessary to make good use of external opportunities, such as the global sustainable development trend, the increasing consumer demand for green products, because these are all factors with high weights and high scores (3-4). Some challenges that need attention, such as competition from large competitors, difficulty in accessing capital, lack of market information and climate change/socio-economic situation, are factors with high weights but low scores (2), showing potential risks that can hinder development.

Table 3. EFAS Matrix Assessment According to 4 Business Start-Up Areas

External factors	Weight	Commerce	Manufacture	Service	Agriculture, forestry and fishery
Sustainable development trends	0.10	0.40	0.30	0.40	0.30
Support from government, organizations	0.10	0.30	0.30	0.40	0.30
Demand for green products increases	0.12	0.48	0.36	0.48	0.36
Building brand and reputation	0.08	0.24	0.24	0.32	0.24
Innovation, technology	0.10	0.30	0.40	0.40	0.30
Developing consumer markets	0.08	0.24	0.24	0.32	0.24
Smart consumption trends	0.07	0.21	0.21	0.28	0.21
New technology (AI, e-commerce...)	0.07	0.21	0.21	0.28	0.14
Local startup policy	0.10	0.30	0.20	0.30	0.20
Support from school/incubator	0.08	0.24	0.24	0.32	0.24
Competition from big rivals	0.10	0.20	0.30	0.20	0.20
Difficulty accessing capital	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.20	0.20
Lack of market information	0.08	0.16	0.16	0.16	0.16
Climate change, socio-economics	0.10	0.20	0.20	0.30	0.20
Total	1	3.68	3.56	4.36	3.29

Source: Synthesis of the author group

Based on the results of a survey of 1,000 students and interviews with 4 experts, the team built a green evaluation criteria table as shown in Table 4.

Table 4. Table of Criteria for Evaluating Green Business Startup Ideas

No.	Observation name	Variable code
1	Green Potential Profit	TC1
2	Green market share	TC2
3	Green competition	TC3
4	Green consumption appeal	TC4
5	Green supply	TC5
6	Green economic efficiency	TC6
7	Green time	TC7
8	Green trend	TC8
9	Green location	TC9
10	Green Value and Innovation	TC10
11	Green Real Needs	TC11
12	Green self-reliance	TC12
13	Green background	TC13

Source: Proposal of the author group

In this study, a scale of 1 to 9 (Sodhi and Prabhakar, 2012) will be used to convert linguistic variables into Fuzzy numbers. In which, the selected conversion ranges include 5 intervals to perform pairwise comparison between fuzzy parameters (Table 5).

Table 5. Table of Linguistic Variables and Corresponding Fuzzy Numbers

Language variation	Variable symbol	Language variable code	The corresponding triangular fuzzy numbers	Inverse of triangular fuzzy numbers
Equally important	BN	1	(1, 1, 3)	(1/3, 1/1, 1/1)
More important	TH	3	(1, 3, 5)	(1/5, 1/3, 1/1)
More important	NH	5	(3, 5, 7)	(1/7, 1/5, 1/3)
Very important	RT	7	(5, 7, 9)	(1/9, 1/7, 1/5)
Extremely important	CT	9	(7, 9, 9)	(1/9, 1/9, 1/7)

Source: Proposal of the author group

The criteria groups are classified logically to ensure the connection with the EFAS matrix. Green business startup ideas are selected according to 4 business areas, for evaluation: production ideas, trade ideas, service ideas, agriculture, forestry and fishery ideas will be denoted as YTSX, YTTM, YTDV, YTNLNN respectively. The results of the standardized matrix construction are shown in Table 6 (Appendix).

Based on the results, the priority level of criteria TC1, TC2, TC3 and TC4 greatly affects the evaluation of green business startup ideas. If focusing on service ideas, TC6 is the criterion that should be improved. For ideas that need to take advantage of natural resources, attention should be paid to TC12 and TC13 because they have a fairly high weighted score.

Based on the results of the proximity index, it shows that commercial ideas (YTTM) are the most optimal choice for students to start a green business with $CC_i = 0.692$. Meanwhile, service ideas (YTDV) and agriculture, forestry and fishery ideas (YTNLNN) have an average level of suitability ($CC_i = 0.500$) that students can consider choosing. On the contrary, production ideas (YTSX)

ranked last with the lowest CCI (0.464), showing that the level of access to start-ups is still limited and input factors need to be adjusted if we want to improve the feasibility of this group of ideas.

Table 7. Priority Ranking of Green Business Startup Ideas by Sector

No.	Business Startup Field
1	Commercial ideas
2	Service ideas
3	Agriculture, forestry and fishery ideas
4	Production ideas

Source: Proposal of the author group

Solutions to Promote the Choice of Green Business Startup Ideas for Students at Universities in Hanoi City

In order to enhance and promote the choice of green business start-up ideas for students at universities in Hanoi in the coming time, the group of authors proposes a number of solutions including:

First, increase potential green profits by creating green products/services to increase the attractiveness to attract consumers.

Second, expand green market share by optimally meeting consumer needs.

Third, compete green according to three criteria including not undermining competitors, optimizing business processes, and products that create added value for customers.

Fourth, create green consumer appeal through communication campaigns and green marketing activities.

Five, establish a stable and sustainable green supply chain to optimize costs to create stable profits and low maintenance costs.

Six, increase green economic efficiency by minimizing production and operating costs.

Seven, determine the ideal green time and timing to start a business, based on green resources combined to create products/services, satisfying green trends at green locations suitable for consumer needs.

Eight, create green trends by building a value system that green products/services bring to consumers to create a sustainable ecosystem of benefits for businesses, society and consumers.

Nine, choose a green location with a large concentration of consumers and convenient for travel.

Tenth, innovate green thinking by creating feasible green products/services that meet the actual needs of consumers. Eleventh, based on personal green self-reliance, choose business startup ideas that are suitable for the green context to minimize risks and increase the chance of success.

Twelfth, promote communication and raise awareness of green business, to change students' awareness and attitude towards green business startups.

Thirteenth, strengthen support for green business start-up training for students, combining theory and practice through start-up projects with expert advice.

Fourteenth, build a network connecting the green business start-up community by establishing start-up clubs, to create a bridge between students and stakeholders.

Tenth, encourage research and application of green technology between university departments and research labs with start-up businesses, creating conditions for effective technology transfer.

References

Gantt, H. L. (1910). *Work, wages, and profits: Their influence on the cost of living*. New York, NY: Engineering Magazine Co.

Zadeh, L. A. (1965). Fuzzy sets. *Information and Control*, 8(3), 338–353. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-9958\(65\)90241-X](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0019-9958(65)90241-X)

Sodhi, M. S., & Prabhakar, A. (2012). AHP–Fuzzy approach for evaluating service quality in academic libraries. *International Journal of Productivity and Quality Management*, 10(4), 519–540.

Kerzner, H. (2017). *Project management: A systems approach to planning, scheduling, and controlling* (12th ed.). Hoboken, NJ: John Wiley & Sons.

Saaty, T. L. (1980). *The analytic hierarchy process: Planning, priority setting, resource allocation*. New York, NY: McGraw-Hill.

Hwang, C. L., & Yoon, K. (1981). *Multiple attribute decision making: Methods and applications*. New York, NY: Springer-Verlag.

Appendix

Table 6. Decision Matrix Table According to Criteria

Variable name	Decision matrix				Normalization matrix				MT normalized weights			
	YTSX	YTTM	YTDV	YTNLNN	YTSX	YTTM	YTDV	YTNLNN	YTSX	YTTM	YTDV	YTNLNN
TC1	8.5	7.0	8.5	5.5	0.568	0.468	0.568	0.368	0.083	0.068	0.083	0.054
TC2	8.0	8.0	7.0	5.5	0.529	0.529	0.463	0.363	0.059	0.059	0.052	0.041
TC3	8.5	8.5	8.0	4.5	0.563	0.562	0.529	0.298	0.042	0.042	0.039	0.022
TC4	8.0	8.0	7.5	3.5	0.570	0.570	0.535	0.271	0.046	0.046	0.043	0.022
TC5	6.0	8.5	6.5	4.0	0.467	0.660	0.505	0.311	0.035	0.050	0.038	0.023
TC6	4.0	8.0	9.0	2.0	0.317	0.634	0.713	0.158	0.023	0.046	0.052	0.011
TC7	4.0	9.0	7.5	2.5	0.297	0.668	0.557	0.186	0.018	0.041	0.034	0.011
TC8	4.0	8.0	9.0	4.5	0.298	0.690	0.670	0.334	0.017	0.040	0.039	0.019
TC9	3.5	6.5	8.0	4.0	0.302	0.561	0.632	0.316	0.019	0.036	0.041	0.020
TC10	4.0	8.0	8.0	4.0	0.315	0.622	0.622	0.311	0.020	0.040	0.040	0.020
TC11	4.5	8.0	8.5	3.0	0.378	0.623	0.644	0.252	0.024	0.040	0.041	0.016
TC12	2.0	7.5	7.5	5.0	0.168	0.562	0.562	0.374	0.009	0.030	0.030	0.020
TC13	5.0	8.0	8.0	4.5	0.380	0.608	0.608	0.342	0.020	0.032	0.032	0.018

Source: Proposal of the author group

